

Some Aspects of Bioactive Marine Natural Products^Ψ

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Marine natural products have attracted the attention of chemists and biologists worldwide for the last four decades. To date over 6500 marine natural products have been isolated from marine organisms. Several of them exhibit biological activity. Some of them have biomedical potential.

Marine organisms not only elaborate pharmaceutically useful compounds but also produce toxic substances. One of the most important societal contributions of marine natural products had been the isolation and identification of marine toxins responsible for seafood poisonings. Outbreak of seafood poisoning are usually sporadic and unpredictable because toxic fish or shellfish do not produce the toxins themselves, but concentrate from organisms that they eat. Most marine toxins are produced by microorganisms such as dinoflagellates or marine bacteria, and may pass through several levels of the food-chains till they reach the humans. The identification of marine toxins has been one of the most challenging areas of marine natural products chemistry.

The major occupation of marine natural products chemists for the past three decades had been the search for potential pharmaceuticals. It is difficult to single out a particular bioactive molecule from marine organisms that is destined to find a place in medicine. However, many compounds have shown promise. Marine organisms produce some of the most cytotoxic compounds ever discovered, but the yields of these compounds are invariably so small that natural sources are unlikely to provide enough material for drug development studies.

The art by which marine organisms elaborate bioactive molecules is fascinating. Marine environment provides different biosynthetic conditions to organisms that live in it. Marine organisms live in symbiotic association. The pathway of transfer of nutrients between symbiotic partners is of great importance and raise questions about the real origin of the metabolites produced by association. A recent trend in marine natural products chemistry is the study of symbiosis. The biosynthesis of bioactive marine natural products provides many challenging problems.

The biological activity of an extract of marine organisms or isolated compounds could be assessed in several ways. Due to limited amount of the material generally available initially and high cost of biological testing, it is impossible for any laboratory to examine *in vivo* all permutation of drug-animal interaction, to unmask the drug poten-

tial of a material. Further, the candidate drug has to pass through rigorous toxicological evaluation and clinical trials before it reaches clinician's armamentarium. A fair understanding of biological, toxicological and clinical evaluation is essential to those interested in searching potential drugs from marine organisms.

Marine algae

About 30000 species of algae are found in the world. They occur everywhere where there is light and moisture, and are found in abundance in seas. In sea water many algae grow as phytoplankton (especially the dinoflagellates and certain blue-green algae). Other marine algae grow as benthos, epiphytes on other algae, rocks, stones, gravels and sand. A small group of algae occurs in brackish water.

Cyanophyta (blue-green algae) are more common in tropical waters than in temperate regions. Many blue-green algae are free-floating and microscopic, and may grow so abundantly that they form a dense scum on the surface of water in the form of a bloom imparting an intense blue-green colour to it.

Rhodophyta (red algae) have about 400 genera, and a majority of which grow in salt water and form a conspicuous vegetation in the littoral and sublittoral zones. They prefer temperate and colder seas and generally grow on rocky stones.

Xanthophyta (yellow-green algae) is a much smaller group as compared to chlorophyta.

Phaeophyta (brown algae) have about 200 genera. Different species of brown algae grow in different ecological conditions.

Chlorophyta (green algae) exhibit a wide range of thal-
lus organization. They may be microscopic, unicellular, motile forms.

Biological, toxicological and clinical evaluations

The basic premises of a screening program are : (i) drug operates in a dose response manner and produce toxicity in higher doses, (ii) each class of drug has a characteristic dose response profile, (iii) for majority of drugs, route of administration produces only a quantitative change in action, (iv) absolute potency is not of major importance in therapeutics and (v) it is possible to predict usefulness and toxicity of a new compound by utilizing a dose response spectra library of various prototype drugs.

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The criteria of a good screening program are that it should be simple, economical, reliable, pick up new unexpected or unique activity, unbiased and comprehensive, and finally it should have in-built safety mechanisms.

The primary screening of an extract or a compound is mainly descriptive and qualitative. In depth evaluation is carried out at the secondary screening.

Types of screening :

Individual activity screening : It is conducted to detect a particular biological property of an extract or compound such as antibacterial, antiviral, anticancer, antifertility etc.

Broad biological screening : It is conducted to know whether an extract or compound has any exploitable biological potential.

Antibacterial and antifungal activities : The need for effective antibacterial and antifungal drug has been realized more acutely with the emergence of Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS) and AIDS Related Complex (ARC) which are often associated with opportunistic infections.

Antileishmanial activity : Leishmaniasis is caused by invasion of the hemoflagellate protozoan parasite, *Leishmania donovani*. The parasite is transmitted by the sandfly of the genus *Phlebotomus* sp. Humans are the main reservoir of the infection.

In leishmaniasis a peculiar situation occurs where the invader amastigote thrives and multiplies within the macrophages, the cells which normally destroy invaders. This adaptation not only deranges host's defense system but even defeats man's ingenuity in directing and delivering drug at the appropriate site.

Both promastigotes and amastigotes are used as test parasites for *in vitro* testing. *In vivo* testing is conducted in mouse and hamster.

Antiviral activity : Theoretically the test material can be evaluated in any test system by combination of virus and susceptible host system. However, it is suggested that the potential antiviral agent must not be evaluated in inert medium but in a living cell or animal host.

Testing for antiviral activity is usually conducted in cell culture; chicken eggs and animal models. Each test method has its advantages and disadvantages. Several viral targets are studied to estimate the antiviral effect of a test substance in a cell culture system. Some of these are viral DNA polymerase, ribonucleotide diphosphate reductase; mRNA polyadenylate and RNA- dependent RNA polymerase; terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase; thymidine kinase; uracyl DNA-glycolase; d-UTPase and reverse transcriptase.

Testing in animal models has relatively the maximum predictive value. The ideal animal model should have three features : (i) human virus with minimal alteration by adap-

tation, (ii) natural route of infection and size of inoculum as in man and (iii) similarity of course of infection, such as host response, drug metabolism and drug toxicity. Animal models are available for both local and systemic virus infections. Antiviral activity of a test substance can also be assessed by titrating the virus in blood and other target organs.

Anti-inflammatory activity : The knowledge about the inflammatory process is still fragmentary. The drugs that are being used for its treatment have been found either by accidental clinical observation or by screening in animals. A number of *in vivo* screening models are available. However, none of the tests reported so far have achieved the ideal.

Gastric irritation test : Gastric irritation is the most important side-effect of antiarrhythmic drugs and therefore, any potential drug must be subjected to this test.

Antiallergic activity : Allergic conditions such as bronchial asthma, atopic eczema, allergic rhinitis, conjunctivitis, urticaria etc. affect about 20% of the population and are increasing in prevalence and severity. In spite of significant progress in the field of new drug development in recent years, there is still no satisfactory antiallergic drug available for therapeutic use.

Antiarrhythmic and antithrombotic activities : In spite of recent advances in diagnostic and investigative cardiology, the life threatening ventricular arrhythmias still present a therapeutic problem. Although the available antiarrhythmic drugs are useful in reducing the incidence of cardiac arrhythmias, the successful treatment with minimal side-effects is still far from satisfactory. Evaluation of antiarrhythmic potential drugs is difficult because animal models do not necessarily mimic those seen in humans, and further we still have poor understanding of mechanism of clinical arrhythmias. However, there are a number of animal models of wide diversity for testing extracts or pure compounds for evaluating antiarrhythmic activity.

Hypolipidaemic activity : There is no single model for testing lipid lowering activity of a test substance. Several experimental models for primary screening *in vivo* are conducted for evaluating the activity. The tests are conducted in triton induced hyperlipoproteinemia in male rats.

Adaptogenic and immunomodulatory activities : Much before the concept of immunity was known, a large number of plants were being used in the traditional medicine of Europe, China and India for rejuvenation therapy and treatment of chronic ailments. Immunostimulants offer promise in enhancing antigen specific non-specific immune response against infection and malignancy, immunotherapy of viral infection and potentiating the efficacy of drugs in immunocompromised host.

Immunomodulators are substances which have potential to modulate an immune response *in vivo* and/or *in vitro*. Since the development of a particular immune response is a multistep process and regulated at several levels through various mechanisms, immunomodulators may act at different steps/levels of the overall immune network. Therefore, a large battery of assay may be required to evaluate the immunomodulator activity.

Hepatoprotective activity: The biochemical and physiological functions of liver and the activity of a wide range of hepatic enzymes are altered when the animals are exposed to chemicals such as carbon tetrachloride, D-galactosamine, thioacetamide, heavy metals, drugs such as paracetamol, fungal toxins, and parasitic infections.

The available models for evaluating the hepatoprotective activity are: carbon tetrachloride, D-galactosamine, *Plasmodium berghei* infection, paracetamol, thioacetamide, monocrotaline and aflatoxin B₁.

Anticancer activity: The Cancer Chemotherapy National Service Centre (CCNSC), National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD, U.S.A. has the biggest organisational capability for evaluating the extracts of plants both marine and terrestrial, marine animals and synthetic compounds. The program was intended to give service in academic institutions, research institutes and pharmaceutical industry which lacked resources to follow up their investigations. Since there was not enough information available for extensive rational drug design based on biology and chemistry of tumor cells, CCNSC decided to follow an empirical approach based on screening large number of materials. It was soon realized that natural products were an excellent source of complex chemicals with a wide variety of biological activities. The status of plant and animal extracts by NCI till January 1981 was as follows: total plant extracts screened, 114045, and activity confirmed 4897 (4.3%); total animal extracts screened, 16196, and activity confirmed 660 (4.1%).

The decision of CCNSC to include natural products extracts proved to be very wise. Many active compounds with unusual structure and worthy of development to clinical trials were discovered. This opened up new areas for investigation of related compounds as anticancer agents and also provided new biochemical tools for cell biology. Although many compounds of both natural and synthetic origin were discovered which had good activity in the experimental models only a small number proved useful in the clinic. Hence there is continuing need for searching active compounds with novel structure.

Use of terminology in anticancer screening:

There is a great deal of loose usage of terminology with reference to *in vitro* and *in vivo* anticancer activity as pointed

out by Suffness and Douros¹. Many compounds are cited as anticancer or antitumor agents which are, in fact, only cytotoxic to tumor cells *in vitro*. This group of compounds contains a wide variety of toxic substances which display no particular selectivity towards tumor cells as opposed to normal cells and have no hope of being useful anticancer drugs. Suffness and Douros¹ suggested the following terminology to eliminate the confusion. The term anticancer, antitumor or antineoplastic should not be used to express *in vitro* testing results. The use of the term antitumor or antineoplastic should be used in reporting results of *in vivo* testing. The term anticancer should be reserved for reporting clinical trials data in man.

Screening methodology:

The quality of the screening methodology is the most important factor in drug discovery for any type of biological activity. The predictability of the screens for clinical activity is absolutely critical since if the screens identify compounds which are clinically inactive all of the efforts which go into the development of such compounds are wasted. The correlation of screening 'actives' with clinical activity is an extremely difficult process since it takes a number of years from when active compounds are tested until results of clinical trials are available, and the data base is very small since a few compounds ultimately reach clinical trials.

Characteristics of good screening:

There are number of problems encountered in screening extracts of plants and animals. Generally the concentration of active principles in the crude extracts is very low (1 : 1000), therefore, the screen for their detection should be very sensitive, and specific. Further, screen should be selective, and specific. The methodology must be adaptable to materials which are highly colored, tarry, poorly soluble in water and chemically complex.

The pre-screen, screen or bioassay used must be insensitive to the inactive compounds which are potential interfering substances. The assay must also be insensitive to ubiquitous compounds which will give false actives. NCI dropped the Walker 256 model while screening extracts of plants since it was highly sensitive to tannins. The assay chosen must be highly selective and meet the other requirements of any good assay including validity, predictability, correlation, reproducibility, and the cost should be reasonable.

Current approach and testing status:

The current approach at NCI for screening crude extracts is to use a primary *in vivo* assay, the P388 leukemia, and to use *in vitro* systems as bioassay to guide isolation of *in vivo* active compounds. The advantages of a battery of pre-screens are: (i) there is a greater chance to detect novel compounds,

(ii) compounds with differing mechanisms of action can be selected, (iii) identification of known compounds is simplified since only certain classes of compounds show activity in particular pre-screens.

The major bioassays currently in use in the NCI program are the ICB and P388 cell lines. While these *in vitro* systems are excellent bioassays, they are poor screens because of their sensitivity to cytotoxic substances which are devoid of *in vivo* activity.

All novel compounds which are reproducibly active in the P388 leukemia pre-screen are then put to tumor panel testing. There are eight systems in the panel, of which five are mouse tumor lines and three human tumor lines carried in athymic mice.

NCI screens about 10000 new synthetic compounds, and 400 pure natural products per year and about 14000 crude extracts (8000 fermentation, 5000 plants and 1000 marine animals). From 8 to 12 compounds that pass Decision Network 2A as pre-clinical candidates, about 6 to 8 compounds enter clinical trials each year of which slightly less than half are natural products.

Status of marine natural products :

Didemnin-B, a cyclic depsipeptide isolated from the tunicate *Trididemnum solidum* by Rinehart's group² at University of Illinois and Weinheimer's group¹ at University of Houston, is in clinical trials. Didemnin-B is an extremely potent agent, active against the B16 melanoma system in μ /kg dose and has also shown a broad spectrum of activity against stem cells in culture. It is remarkably active as an immunosuppressant, some 1000 times as potent as cyclosporin A in inhibiting T-cell mitogenesis. It has also shown *in vivo* activity in prolonging skin grafts and rat heart transplants¹.

Several other marine peptides had displayed high order of antitumor activity. There are other non-peptidyl marine natural products which had also shown high order of activity in P388 leukemia and appear to have drug potential.

It is expected that the NCI programme will continue to discover novel compounds of natural origin with antitumor activity. It is hoped that these new active compounds will ultimately become clinically useful in cancer treatment as well as novel biochemical probes for the study of tumor cell biology.

Regulatory toxicity :

Regulatory toxicity studies of the test substance are conducted only after the pharmacological activity is confirmed and baseline data are generated regarding the effective dose, lethal dose and maximum tolerated dose. These studies are carried out with the potential drugs before being passed on to clinicians for Phase I and Phase II clinical trials. The

types of studies needed are : acute toxicity, repeated dose study, subacute toxicity, reproductive, teratological prenatal and post-natal, carcinogenic and mutagenic studies.

Clinical trials :

Clinical trials of new candidate drugs for safety and efficacy evaluation are mandatory before a candidate drug is cleared for marketing. However, the need to carry out clinical trials does not justify experimentation in man.

The candidate drugs are approved for clinical practice, after they have been evaluated in different phases of clinical trials. In Phase I clinical trials the tolerability of the test compound in different doses in healthy volunteers is first assayed. Side-effects during the Phase I studies are carefully monitored. In Phase II studies in patients, the therapeutic effects of the test drug are carefully monitored. Phase II clinical trials are only started when data on human volunteers on tolerability, kinetics, metabolism and also its therapeutic efficacy are available. Phase III clinical trials include dose-finding studies. In these clinical trials, data on several thousands patients in various well-defined indications are collected. Finally, if necessary, field studies are also undertaken to have large number of patients treated in life situation. Even after marketing, the performance of a drug has to be followed in post-marketing surveillance for efficacy and rare adverse drug reactions. Thus the journey of a drug candidate starting from displaying activity in biological screening to reach clinician's armamentarium is very long, arduous, time-consuming and expensive.

Bioactivity of marine organisms

Marine organisms display a wide range of biological activities^{4,5}, such as antifertility, antiviral, antibiotic, antifungal, and antimicrobial. The extracts of seaweeds also affect central nervous system. A few growth stimulant properties which may be useful in studies on wound healing and carcinogenic properties in the study of cancers have been mentioned. Many toxins involved in fatal poisoning such as paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP), are produced by a number of dinoflagellates⁶. Ciguatera, a seafood poisoning is caused by ingestion of coral reef fish that have become toxic through diet. It is now established that the toxins are produced by the epiphytic dinoflagellates and transferred to herbivorous fish and subsequently to carnivores through the food-chain⁷. The extracts of marine tunicate exhibit high order of antitumor, antiviral, and immuno-suppressive activities⁸.

Several marine bacteria exhibit antibiotic activity. A red coloured bacterium from Puerto Rico is found to excrete into sea water medium antibacterial substances. The bacteria and fungi are also reported¹ to produce substances which

affect central nervous system, respiratory system, neuromuscular system, cardiovascular system, and gastrointestinal system. Some of the substances are known to produce local effects, such as pain, necrosis, edema, parasthesias, prurites etc.

Broad biological screening of extracts of marine organisms from the Indian coasts, the Andaman and Nicobar Islands, and Lakshadweep, had been carried out at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. The extracts were evaluated for pharmacological, antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, antifertility, antiprotozoal, antihelminthic, diuretic, hypoglycemic, and anti-inflammatory activities. Toxicities of the extracts were also determined⁹. Of the 450 extracts evaluated, 14 exhibited anti-implantation (antifertility), 28 antiviral, 10 CNS depressant, 31 CNS stimulant, 33 diuretic, 10 hypoglycemic, 16 hypotensive, 1 oxytocic, 3 spasmogenic, and 3 spasmolytic activities. Fourteen extracts were found to be toxic⁹.

Biological activities were found in about 25% of the extracts screened. A high order of anti-implantation (antifertility) activity was detected in a number of extracts. Marine organisms displaying high order of biological activity were : antiviral, *Ulva fasciata* and *Chondria armata*; anti-implantation, *Padina tetrastomatica* and *Ischnochiton camпус*; hypotensive, *Gemmaria* spp., *Turbo intestinalis*; diuretic, *Ircinia racemosa*; oxytocic, *Corallina* spp.

Over 300 marine organisms from Okinawan water had been screened for cytotoxicity, antiviral, and antimicrobial activities¹⁰. An extract of a sponge *Theonella* spp. was found highly cytotoxic in the assay against P388 murine leukemia cells. Bioassay guided separation led to the isolation of an active constituent named misokinolide-A which had IC₅₀ 10 ng/ml *in vitro* and T/C 145% at a dose of 0.5 mg/kg against P388 in mice.

Rinehart *et al.*¹¹ had been searching pharmaceutically useful compounds from marine organisms. Their first effort involved a survey of marine organisms for antibacterial and antifungal activities. The bioassay was carried out on shipboard which had many advantages. These were the first systematic shipboard assay for pharmaceutical activity. The most active antiviral extract in shipboard testing was of a tunicate, *Eudistoma olivaceum* but the extract was surprisingly found inactive in the secondary assay. However, the extract of the recollected sample proved very active both in primary and secondary assays against *Herpes simplex* and other viruses confirming the value of on-site assay. The extract of the tunicate *Trididemnum solidum* was found to have potent antiviral activity in bioassay carried out on shipboard¹¹. It was also found to be most cytotoxic. Moreover, these activities were confirmed *in vivo* testing at Upjohn,

U.S.A. Nine major and several minor compounds named didemnins were isolated from the tunicate. Didemnins were active *in vivo* against DNA and RNA viruses. Of these didemnin-B was most active. It displayed remarkable immunosuppressant activity.

Ecteinascidia turbinata was reported to contain a potent antitumor agent. An interesting immunoregulatory activity was subsequently observed in the extract of the organism.

Bioactive metabolites of marine algae

Chemically the bioactive metabolites of marine algae include brominated phenols, oxygen heterocyclics, nitrogen heterocyclics, sulfur-nitrogen heterocyclics, sterols, and proteins¹².

Brominated phenols : The active principles isolated from the green, brown and red algae exhibiting antibacterial and antifungal activities are : 2,3-dibromobenzyl alcohol, 4,5-disulfate dipotassium salt, 2,3-dibromo-4,5-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, 2,3-dibromo-4,5-dihydroxybenzyl alcohol, 3,5-dibromo-*p*-hydroxybenzyl alcohol and 5-bromo-3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde. Virtually nothing is known about the physiological importance of these bromophenols. Their antialgal activity suggests that they might be playing a role in the regulation of epiphytes and endophytes. Brominated compounds from marine algae particularly bromophenols are toxic and due to this they are not of clinical value.

Nitrogen heterocyclics : Marine algae had yielded several bioactive nitrogen heterocyclic compounds. Of these the most interesting compounds are domoic and kainic acids. Domoic acid isolated from the alga *Chondria armata* was characterized as LS-arabo-2-carboxy-4-(1-methyl-5-carboxy-*trans, trans*-5-*trans*-1,3-hexadienyl)-3-pyrrolidine acetic acid. Domoic acid displayed marked antihelminthic activity. It was found to be very effective in expelling ascaris and pinworm without any observable side-effects.

In Asia the dried red alga *Digenea simplex* is widely used as an anthelmintic. It was found very effective in the treatment of ascariasis. In the Mediterranean, extract of the alga *Corallina officinalis* is also used for the same purpose. Kainic acids as the active principles were isolated from these algae. Of the kainic acids, α -kainic acid was the most active constituent. It was found effective in the treatment of ascariasis with a single dose of 5–10 mg per adult resulting in a 40–70% reduction in the population of intestinal parasitic worms. Several preparations of kainic acids are available in the market including 'Digenin' and 'Helminal'. This represents one of the few instances in which clinically useful pharmaceutical products are obtained from marine source.

Guanidine derivatives : Certain shellfish periodically

becomes poisonous to humans. It is now well established that the substance responsible is produced by a marine plankton, *Gonyaulax catenella*. The toxin isolated from the Alaskan butter clam, California mussel, and the alga *G. catenella* is called saxitoxin. Its structure was assigned on the basis of degradation studies and spectroscopic analysis.

Saxitoxin blocks nerve conduction by specifically interfering with increase in sodium permeability of the membrane. The symptoms caused by the toxin included peripheral paralysis. In extreme cases complete loss of strength in the muscles and finally death occurred due to respiratory failure. Saxitoxin is absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. It produced no major vascular action. The oral LD₅₀ for saxitoxin in various species of animals is reported. In man death had occurred following ingestion of as little as 1 mg of toxin.

The toxic compounds from marine algae appear to have biomedical potential. The compounds with neurotropic effects may yield important drugs.

Phenazine derivatives : Several species of *Caulerpa* had yielded bioactive phenazine derivatives. Of these caulerpin and caulerpicine are most important. Caulerpin caused a mild anesthetic action when put in the mouth, it caused numbness of the lips and tongue. In some persons it produced toxic effects. The toxic syndrome were somewhat similar to that produced by ciguatera fish poisoning.

Sulfated polysaccharides : The sulfated polysaccharides obtained from seaweeds are economically most important products due to their extensive use in food and medicine. The red algae produce carrageenan, agar, agarose, Danish agar. Alginic acid is produced by brown algae. It is believed that carrageenans comprise of D-galactose units and derivatives linked alternatively (1 → 3) and β(1 → 4). The *iota*, *kappa*, *lambda* and *mu* and other carrageenans basically have the same general structure in which the galactose units are sulfated in a definite pattern and/or are present in the 3,6-anhydro form. Carrageenan is expressed generally as an A-B-A polymer. There are other views also about the structure of these sulfated polysaccharides. The chemical structures of *kappa* and *lambda* carrageenans are still a matter of discussion. However, both the carrageenans are reported to be strong antigens. *Lambda* carrageenan in addition also stimulates the growth of connective tissues. Carrageenan from *Chondrus crispus* and *Gelidium cartilagineum* has antiviral properties. It is active against influenza B and mumps viruses. It is also an anticoagulant and antithrombic agent. The use of carrageenan in ulcer therapy had been studied intensively. It is believed that the polysaccharide reacts with mucoid lining of the stomach and gives a protection layer.

Alginic acid : Chemically alginic acid is made up of two monomers, the D-mannuronic acid and L-guluronic acid. Both the sugar acids are stereoisomers and differ only in the configuration of the carboxyl group. The two uronic acid moieties in alginic acid are linked through β-1,4-glycosidic linkage in such a way that the carboxyl group of each unit is free while the aldehydic group is shielded by the glycosidic bond. Biosynthesis of alginic acid is not yet known.

Commercially sodium alginate is extracted from giant brown seaweed *Macrocystis pyrifera*, horsetail kelp (*Laminaria digitata*) and sugar kelp (*Laminaria saccharina*). The largest use of sodium alginate is in the manufacture of icecream where it serves as a stabilizing colloid. It is also used in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals. Calcium alginate is a hemostatic agent which stimulates the clotting of blood *in situ* and is subsequently absorbed in the tissues. Sodium alginate is used as an adjuvant in immunization against two strains of influenza virus and is also found effective in diminishing hypercalciuria in urolithiasis and in the treatment of esophagitis.

The most significant property of sodium alginate of biomedical value is that it has the ability to remove strontium 85 and 87 from the body without seriously affecting the availability of Ca, Na or K in the body. This selective action of sodium alginate is of great potential value in the removal of Sr-90 contamination due to fallout from atomic explosions.

Laminarin : It is essentially a linear polymer of β-1,3-glucan, with occasional branching at C-6 and with a variable proportion of the glucose chains terminated at the potential reducing end with a molecule of mannitol, which can be sulfated to produce a compound with anticoagulant properties. Laminarin occurs at certain times of the year to the extent of 35% of the dry weight of *Laminaria cloustoni*. Laminarin sulfate formed with two sulfate groups on glucose unit gives maximum stability and strong anticoagulant property.

Agar and agarose : The red algae are the source of agar and agarose. Their use in biomedical research is well known. Chemically agarose is a linear polymer, made up of repeating units of agarobiose. Many uses of agarose are described. However, its use in immunology is most interesting.

Marine bacteria and fungi

Bacteria and fungi are prime producers of the antagonistic substances in terrestrial environment. A similar role in the oceans of these organisms are expected. Indeed, this has been found true. Antibiotic, antiviral, antifungal, and antiyeast activities of these organisms had been reported. In addition, a few growth-stimulant properties which may be useful in studies on wound healing, carcinogenic proper-

ties, useful in the study of cancers, are mentioned.

A marine isolate of the fungus *Cephalosporium acremonium* from the sea near a sewage outfall of the coast of Sardina had been reported to produce a number of antibiotic substances named as cephalosporins P₁, P₂, P₃, P₄ and P₅.

Several bacteria which produce antibiotic substances had been isolated from shallow water near Puerto Rico. A bromopyrrole antibiotic from *Pseudomonas bromoutilis* displayed activity against many Gram-positive bacteria. The bromo compound was unique in that over 70% of its weight consisted of covalently bonded bromine.

The formation of antibiotic substances of the types mentioned above gives the indication that the marine microbes are capable of producing new and unusual types of antibiotic substances than the terrestrial ones. Some of these bioactive substances would be found undoubtedly useful in medicine and pharmacology, while others could serve as model for synthesis of new structures which conceivably would be of even greater interest than native products.

Current status of bioactive metabolites. phytoplanktons

Studies on the chemistry of marine phytoplanktons are few because of difficulty of growing the organisms and the low yield of secondary metabolites. In spite of these limitations some most potent toxins had been isolated from these sources. For example, *Gonyaulax* species had yielded saxitoxin, neosaxitoxin, gonyautoxins-I-IV etc. From the cell culture of the dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium breve*, brevetoxin B, C and dihydrobrevetoxin B and related compounds had been isolated. A unique feature of their structures is a chain of eleven continuous *trans*-fused ether rings in the form of a flat ladder.

Blue-green algae : *Lyngbya majuscula* known to cause swimmer's itch had furnished several classes of compounds such as lyngbyatoxin, aplysiatoxin, majusculamide etc.

Cytotoxic and fungicidal nucleosides, tubercidin, toycamycin, and their 5'- α -D-glucopyranose derivatives had been isolated from several blue-green algae.

Green algae : Tropical green algae and a few of their temperate relatives had yielded a number of bioactive metabolites¹. The characteristic features of these metabolites are the presence of a 1,4-diacetoxybutadiene moiety. Several species of the genus *Halimeda* produce the trialdehyde helimedatrial, an ichthyotoxin which inhibited the growth of marine bacteria and fungi, cell division of fertilized sea-urchin eggs and the motility of sea-urchin sperm at 1 μ g/ml.

Brown algae : A large number of prenylated quinones, hydroquinones and other compounds had been isolated from brown algae.

Several highly unsaturated C₁₁ hydrocarbon had been isolated from a mixed collection of *Dictyopteris plagiogramma* and *D. australis*. It had been observed that the sperm cells aggregate around the female gametes of brown algae which exude C₁₁ hydrocarbons. The female gametes attracted the sperm cells and caused them to remain in the excited state in the vicinity of the latter. The attractants identified are : ectocarpene, fucoserratene, multibidene, desmarestene and finavarrene.

Tracing the origin of arsenic in lobsters and in fish, it was found that the brown alga *Ecklonia radiata* concentrated arsenic in the form of arsenosugars.

Red algae : Marine red algae had furnished a vast array of halogenated compounds.

5-Iodo-5'-deoxytubercidin, an unusual nucleoside isolated from *Hypnea valenteae* caused pronounced relaxation of muscles and hypothermia in mice and blocked polysynaptic and monosynaptic reflexes.

Micro-algae : Micro-algae represent a sub-set of single cell microorganisms. These are ubiquitous in nature. There are over 50000 species of micro-algae of which only a few had been characterized.

Micro-algae are a major untapped source of bioactive compounds and valuable biochemicals. One future commercial application of micro-algae could be in the production of special lipids. The omega-3-fatty acids found in the oils of certain cold water marine fish are considered to be responsible to reduce incidence of coronary heart disease. These fatty acids are likely to originate from the phytoplankton in food chain. Micro-algae are being used for the production of labelled biochemicals. These labelled compounds have high value. If diagnostic tests are developed using these compounds, the market will increase dramatically. Micro-algae are also expected to furnish potent antiviral, anti-AIDS, antibiotic and other bioactive agents.

Marine algae are, therefore, of considerable interest to scientists interested both in basic and applied research. Several products of commercial value are produced from marine algae. There are several possibilities for commercial production of micro-algae and/or their products. This opens a vast area for the commercial production of products of high value as well as products of food industry from marine micro-algae.

Bioactive metabolites of marine invertebrates

The marine invertebrates which have yielded potent bioactive compounds are : marine sponges, jellyfish, sea anemones, corals, bryozoans, molluscs, echinoderma, tunicates and crustaceans. The bioactive compounds isolated from these marine organisms could be divided into steroids,

terpenoids, isoprenoids, nonisoprenoids, quinones, brominated compounds, nitrogen heterocyclics and nitrogen-sulfur heterocyclics¹³⁻¹⁸.

Steroids : The gonads of many fish species are known to contain testosterone, progesterone, estradiol-17 β , esterone, estriol and androstenedione. The plasma of various fish species contains cortisol, cortisone, progesterone testosterone etc.

Saponins : Several species of sea cucumber (Holothuroidea) are eaten in many parts of the world. Occasionally these sea cucumbers become poisonous. A peculiar gland found in these animals named after the zoologist Cuvier, is particularly rich in toxins. Sea cucumber probably use this poison for their defence against predators. A number of saponins from the water-soluble extract of Cuvier gland of *Actinopyga agassizi*, a holothurian found in Bham Islands had been isolated and characterized. It is reported that although these saponins are poisonous, however, they are not responsible for the occasional poisoning caused by sea cucumbers.

Holothurian saponins are steroidal saponins and named holothurins. Hydrolysis of the saponins gave one mole of sulfuric acid and D-glucose, D-xylose, D-glucomethylose (quinovose) and 3-O-methylglucose as sugar moieties. Holothurins are considered to have good anticancer and pharmaceutical potential such as neuromuscular properties. Since the biological action of holothurins was vested in the steroidal moiety of the molecule, it is hoped that one may find some useful chemotherapeutic agents from sea cucumber species.

Terpenoids : The extracts of gorgonians which showed antibiotic activity had furnished a number of bioactive terpenoids. The diterpene, eunicin and crassin acetate exhibited antibacterial and antiamebic activities respectively.

It had been suggested that the terpenoid lactones and sesquiterpenoids may be functional antibiotics in living gorgonians. The relatively high concentrations of some antibiotic substances in these organisms and their potency suggest that further studies to explore their biomedical potential are warranted.

Marine prostaglandins : Chemically prostaglandins are C₂₀ carboxylic acids consisting of a five-membered ring with two side-chains. One of them is of seven carbon atoms and the other of eight carbon atoms. All prostaglandins may be regarded as derivatives of prostanic acid, a trivial name. Prostaglandins display a wide range of biological effects in concentrations as low as 10⁻⁹ μ . They all are biologically active. The biological activities of prostaglandins remained of academic interest till 1971. It was then demonstrated that prostaglandins play a crucial role in causing inflammation.

This finding caught the attention of several workers and the studies of the properties of prostaglandins snow-balled at a very fast pace. Among the prostaglandins, the PG E₂ and PG F₂ are mainly involved in the manifestation of inflammation, pain and swelling. The PGs are also involved in causing fever.

In 1969, Weinheimer and Spraggins¹⁹ reported the first high-yield isolation of non-mammalian type (15R)-PG A₂ and its methyl acetate from the Caribbean gorgonian *Plexaura homomalla* (Esper). This report stimulated worldwide search of PGs in marine life and a number of PGs were isolated from marine organisms. PG E₂ and PG F₂ were even isolated from Australian red alga *Gracilaria lichenoides*²⁰. This was the first report of the occurrence of PGs in plant. The red soft coral *Lobophyton depressum*²⁰ was found to contain PG E₂ 11-acetate methyl ester and its 18-acetoxy derivative. The Hawaiian octocoral *Telestaria riisei*²¹ yielded a series of highly functionalized halogenated prostaglandins, named punaglandins. The Okinawan soft coral *Clavularia viridis* afforded a number of prostaglandins, named claviridenones²². The origin of primary prostaglandins in marine organisms raises many intriguing biochemical questions. The yield of PG A₂ methyl ester in *P. homomalla* was abnormally very high (upto 2% of dry weight of the coral). Punaglandins isolated from the octacoral displayed significant anti-inflammatory activity. Chlorovulone-1 displayed pronounced antitumor activity against HL-60 cells. They also displayed the growth-inhibitory activity against L-1210 leukemia culture cells.

Several mammalian prostaglandins had been isolated from marine organisms. Since all mammalian prostaglandins display biological activities, the marine organisms which contain these mammalian prostaglandins displayed the same activity.

There is great interest in *P. homomella* as a potential commercial source of PGs either by pruning in natural or by marine farming. Marine prostanoids are rich source for supplying materials for the synthesis of biologically useful prostaglandins and their analogs.

Brominated compounds : Many species of sponges are long lived and are resistant to bacterial decomposition. They were suspected to produce antimicrobial substances. Indeed, this was found true, the extracts of a large number of sponges showed a broad spectrum antimicrobial activity. A variety of compounds containing bromine and having broad antibiotic activity, had been isolated from sponges.

The sponge *Dysidea herbacea* from western Carolina Islands contained antibacterial compounds active against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. These antibacterial compounds were found to be brominated deriva-

tives of 2-phenoxyphenol. The sponges *Aplysia aerophoba* and *Verongia thiona* had yielded an antibiotic substance named aerotionin which had a spirocyclohexadienylisoxazole skeleton. The marine sponge *Phakellia flagellata* found in Great Barrier Reef had furnished several interesting bromine-containing alkaloids. Although these alkaloids had a guanidine unit in the five-membered ring D, they did not exhibit the usual high basicity of guanidium moiety. The brominated compounds from marine animals generally had a broad antibiotic spectrum. However, most of them are toxic. No antibiotic substance from a marine sponge had ever reached the stage of clinical verification, and none of the agents, thus far, reported seem to have such a potential.

Nitrogen heterocyclics :

The most important members of this class of compounds are tetrodotoxins and saxitoxins.

Tetrodotoxin : The toxin was known for many years. Its origin until recently was pufferfish (family tetraodontidae). In recent past several derivatives of tetrodotoxin had been isolated from crabs, an octopus, a goby, molluscs, flatworms and even a terrestrial amphibian, all suggesting its origin from microbial source.

Tetrodotoxin had a monomeric structure and contained two molecules in zwitterion form per unit cell. This structure was established by Woodward and Gougoutas²³ through X-ray crystallographic studies. The chemistry of tetrodotoxin is very interesting. Three nitrogen atoms in tetrodotoxin are present as a guanidine moiety. Despite the presence of this function, the compound is weakly basic (pK_a 8.5). Further, the pK_a of the hydrobromide increased to 9.2 in aqueous dioxan. These facts indicate its zwitterionic nature. Tetrodotoxin is readily absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. It altered the initial increase in sodium permeability of the membranes, which resulted in nerve block. It is used clinically as a pain-relieving agent in cases of patients suffering from neurogenic form of Hansen's disease (leprosy). Tetrodotoxin is a useful tool for the analysis of events which occur in the nerves. It may also provide information useful in understanding the mechanism of selective membrane permeability.

Saxitoxin : The toxin had been isolated both from marine plants and marine animals. Earlier it was isolated from marine dinoflagellate *Gonyaulax catenella*. Subsequently, it was isolated from Californian mussels, Alaska butter clams and toxic crabs.

Saxitoxin contains a perhydropurine nucleus, which incorporates two guanidinium moieties. It is transparent in uv and is very labile to bases in the presence of air. On the

basis of degradation studies coupled with physicochemical studies the structure was assigned to saxitoxin²³. Saxitoxin blocks nerve conduction by specifically interfering with the initial increase in sodium permeability of these membrane. Saxitoxin produced effects on the cardiovascular system and a marked hypotensive effect at a very low concentration, 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$.

Marine nucleosides

Bergmann and Feeney²⁵ in 1950 for the first time isolated an unusual nucleoside named spongothymidine from the sponge *Cryptotethia crypta*. This pioneering work stimulated wide interest in the sponges as a source of novel compounds. In recent past several nucleosides with unusual structure had been isolated from marine organisms²⁶. Biological activities found in the marine nucleosides have been a stimulus for the synthesis of various analogs of these nucleosides for biological evaluation²⁷.

The heterocyclic moiety in bioactive marine nucleosides is either a substituted pyrimidine, purine or pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine. The sugar moiety is either D-arabinose, D-ribose, 2'-deoxyribose or 2',3'-didehydro-2',3'-dideoxyribose, or substituted xylose. In mycalisine-A and mycalisine-B the sugar moiety is 3'-*O*-methyl-5-deoxyerythropen-4-enofuranose. In the nucleoside isolated from the kidney of the giant clam *Tridacna maxima*, the hydroxy group at position-5 of D-ribose was substituted with 5-dimethylarsinyl moiety.

Marine nucleosides display antiviral, anticancer, vasodilator, muscle relaxant, and hypotensive activities. Some of them produce bradycardia, and relax smooth muscles. The biological activity of the arabinosides is most prominent. The efficacy of the ara-A in the management of certain human herpes virus infection is firmly established. Ara-A had been found effective in the therapy of herpes keratitis, herpes encephalitis and *Varicella zoaster* infections in immunosuppressed patients. Ara-A is one of the best antiviral drugs known. It had been synthesized prior to its isolation from marine source.

Marine nucleosides have provided new 'Lead compounds' for drug design particularly in the area of viral and parasitic infections. Several analogs of bioactive marine nucleosides had been synthesized and evaluated for biological activities²⁷. The structure-activity relationship studies had furnished very useful information for optimization of the activity. The studies carried out had shown that the analogs of marine nucleosides display high order of antiviral, anticancer, antileishmanial and antiallergic activities.

Marine peptides

Despite excitement generated by the isolation of arabinonucleosides from sponge, the early literature was dominated by reports of non-nitrogenous metabolites which included halogenated terpenes and fatty acid derivatives from red algae and sea hares, cembranes and eicosanoids from coelenterates, sesquiterpenes from sponges, and nudibranchs and diterpenes from brown algae. Only a few reports on isolation of nitrogenous metabolites from marine source led to believe that marine organisms synthesize a few nitrogenous metabolite because nitrogen is a limiting nutrient in the ocean. However, later researches revealed that it was not true. A diverse array of nitrogenous metabolites including nucleosides²⁶, alkaloids^{16,28,31}, isonitriles^{13,14,18}, guanidino¹⁶, amino acids¹⁶ and peptides^{16,32} were isolated from marine organisms.

Blue green algae were found to be a rich source of bioactive peptides. Among the marine invertebrates, sponges and ascidians were good sources of bioactive peptides. The sponge peptides were generally highly modified. It is believed that some sponge peptides are produced by interaction with symbiotic microorganisms.

Over 50 peptides were isolated during last two decades from marine sponges^{21,33}. Several reasons are given for the rapid progress in the chemistry of sponge peptides, such as development of reverse phase HPLC technique for isolation, advances in spectroscopy especially 2D-NMR and FAB mass spectrometry. Chiral chromatography allowed the assignment of absolute configuration of amino acids with small amounts of material. A number of bioactive marine peptides were synthesized. Nazumamide-A, a thrombin-inhibiting linear tetrapeptide was efficiently constructed using diethyl phosphorocyanidate as coupling reagent and *t*-butyloxycarbonyl as *N*-protecting group.

Most of the bioactive marine peptides are cyclic and lipophilic. The chemists involved in the isolation of these peptides were using a specific bioassay method. It is likely that the linear or more polar marine peptides are being missed.

There remain some unanswered questions. Do blue-green algae which live symbiotically with sponges, participate in the synthesis of peptides in sponges? Why are some peptides found in large quantities, while others are present in trace amounts? The answers to some of these questions may come when it will be possible to culture sponge cells or symbiotic microbes. Sponge peptides appear to have drug potential. Cyclotheonamides may serve as 'Lead compounds' for developments of antithrombin drugs. Discodermins are found to be potential antitumor promoting agents and calyculins useful as biochemical reagents.

Ascidians remain unique among marine invertebrates in that they overwhelmingly produce nitrogen-containing metabolites, almost all being derived from amino acids. Although investigations on ascidians as potential source of drugs were initiated more recently than some other marine invertebrates, it is significant that the first marine natural product to enter human clinical trials is didemnin-B, an ascidian cyclic depsipeptide from *Trididemnum solidum*. Ascidians, like many of the other marine invertebrates, are known to exist in obligate and non-obligate symbiosis with microorganisms. The contribution of the symbiotic algae to the biosynthesis of the secondary metabolites of ascidian remains unanswered, because the symbiotic algae had been resistant to culture. However, there had been some success in the mariculture of ascidians.

Most of the bioactive peptides of coelenterates are neurotoxins. They alter the function of Na⁺ channels in excitable membranes of muscles and nerves, and because of this these toxins are considered important probes of Na⁺ channels and related physiological functions.

The *Conus* peptides are used for a wide variety of physiological and pharmacological investigations in both vertebrate and invertebrate nervous systems. Several sperm activating peptides were isolated from sea urchins egg jelly. Resact, the first sea urchin egg jelly derived peptide, was shown to be a chemoattractant agent of animal spermatozoa. Over twenty peptides were isolated from the egg jelly of nine species of sea urchins. It is expected that more species-specific bioactive peptides will be isolated from the egg jelly of sea urchins.

Marine bioactive alkaloids

The field of marine alkaloids is firmly established¹³ and rapidly expanding. Over 40 pyridoacridine alkaloids had been isolated from marine sponge, tunicates, and molluscs³⁴. There is little doubt that their number will increase.

Marine alkaloids, particularly brominated or chlorinated ones do have distinct features as compared to alkaloids from terrestrial sources²⁸. There are ample circumstantial evidences which suggest that some of the marine alkaloids are metabolites of an associated flora. Since the origin of a number of alkaloids is uncertain, the attempts of construction of chemotaxonomical system based on secondary metabolites analysis must be viewed with caution.

Although quite a number of marine alkaloids displayed high order of antineoplastic and antiviral activities, a drug from this source is still very far. However, studies conducted on marine alkaloids had enriched basic organic chemistry, and the biological activities have widened our vision. The biological effects of bioactive marine alkaloids have ex-

panded greatly our knowledge of several basic phenomena in biology. The structures of these bioactive alkaloids have provided fertile area for design and synthesis. The biosynthesis of bioactive marine alkaloids is fascinating and remains unexplored.

Marine toxins

Marine toxins have drawn worldwide attention because of their involvement in human intoxication and the socio-economic impact brought by those incidents³⁵⁻³⁷. Paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) is one of the most severe forms of food poisoning caused by ingestion of seafood. It is acute and often fatal. There is no effective way to destroy the toxins or to treat the patients. Therefore, it poses serious health problems. Detering shellfish consumption causes economic problems. It is now established that saxitoxin, neosaxitoxin and their congeners are involved in paralytic shellfish poisoning. Initially it was thought that PSP was restricted to temperate coastal areas and involved only filter feeding molluscs, recent evidences, however, indicate that the problem is widespread. It is now apparent that the toxins are present not only in molluscs and dinoflagellates but also in zooplankton, crab, algae and a variety of intertidal organisms.

Tetrodotoxin (TTX) because of its frequent involvement in fatal food poisoning, its unique chemical structure and its specific action of blocking sodium channels of excitable membranes is the best known toxins.

Neurotoxic shellfish poisoning : The dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium breve* often forms blooms along the Florida coast and this leads to mass mortality of fish. Large blooms of this organism (red tide) can kill hundreds of tons of fish a day. Sometimes the blooms cause human irritation of eyes and throat in coastal area, and the contamination of shellfish occasionally results in human intoxication. Several toxins named brevetoxins had been isolated from the toxic dinoflagellate, *G. breve*. Brevetoxin-B is made up of a single carbon chain locked into a rigid ladderlike structure consisting of 11 continuous *trans-trans*-fused ether rings.

Ciguatera : The term ciguatera is used to food poisoning caused by ingestion of toxic coral reef fish. Ciguatera not only endangers public health but also hampers local fisheries in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. It is estimated that roughly 20000 people suffer annually from the poisoning. It is now established that ciguatoxin and its congeners and maitotoxin are responsible for this poisoning. Both the groups of toxins are produced by epiphytic dinoflagellate, *Gambierdiscus toxicus* and transferred to herbivorous fish and subsequently to carnivores through the food-chain. Chemically ciguatoxin is a polyether compris-

ing of 13 continuous ether rings.

Maitotoxin had attracted much attention mainly for three reasons. Firstly, it had molecular formula $C_{164}H_{256}O_{68}S_2Na$ and molecular weight of 3422 Da which exceeded that of any other known natural product, and thirdly, it had extremely potent bioactivity. The lethality against mice, LD_{50} was *ca* 50 ng/kg (ip), which suggested that it might be the most potent, non-proteinous toxin. Thus the structure determination of maitotoxin was regarded as one of the most exciting challenges in natural product chemistry.

Palytoxin ($C_{129}H_{223}N_3O_{54}$), M.W. 2678.5 Da, is yet another most potent marine toxin; LD_{50} 0.025 μ g/kg in rabbit and 0.45 mg/kg in mouse. The structure elucidation of palytoxin also posed a tremendous challenge to organic chemists as the toxin had molecular weight of about 3000 dalton but lacked repeating units commonly found in biomolecules of this size.

Diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP) : It is a major public health problem even though it is not lethal. Causative toxins that have been identified are okadaic acid and its congeners and pectenotoxins. Okadaic acid acts as an inhibitor of protein phosphatases.

Remarkable progress has been in recent years in identifying toxigenic sources. It has now been realized that micro-algae play an important role in the marine biological system. Although the most complicated structures of marine toxins have been solved. However, there have been persisting question regarding their true origin. Some of these toxins have been shown not the metabolites of the organisms where they are found, but originate elsewhere. The possible primary producers of these toxins are micro-algae, bacteria and fungi. They are carried through symbiosis, association, food-chain, and other forms of nutrient dependency. Although, immense progress has been made in recent years, many questions remain unanswered, such as the trigger mechanisms for the algal bloom and the toxigenicity.

The contributions of marine toxins to life sciences as biochemical or pharmacological tools have been invaluable.

Biosynthesis of bioactive marine natural products

It is generally believed that the origin and mode of formation of secondary metabolites of marine organisms do not differ substantially from the well-documented biosynthetic pathways of secondary metabolites of terrestrial plants and animals. However, biosynthetic experiments are yet to confirm this assumption.

The marine environment provides different biosynthetic conditions to organisms living in it. The buffering action of sodium carbonate and biocarbonate maintains the pH of

the sea water between 8.2 and 8.5. Sea water contains upto 40% salt and has an osmotic pressure of 15–20 atm. The structure particularly the membrane composition of marine organisms, is expected to differ from their terrestrial counterparts. Further, there are some striking differences between the metabolism of marine and terrestrial organisms. For example, halogen and isocyanide functions are frequently found in the metabolites of marine algae, sponges etc., whereas these functionalities are rarely observed in the metabolites of terrestrial plants and animals. It is not yet known whether these differences reflect the individuality of the producer organisms or are the outcome of evolution.

There are number of problems associated with the biosynthetic studies of marine natural products. For example, the synthesis of metabolites in marine organisms is often slow, particularly if the organism is slow-growing. A long-term feeding experiment is, therefore, essential to get detectable level of incorporation of the precursor into the product. The time of feeding the precursor, is yet another important factor, since metabolites are produced only when the organism is fully developed or when the nutrient levels are high. Fungal and bacterial metabolites are generally produced during stationary growth periods, whereas other metabolites are synthesized during the period of active growth. Although in many cases, the metabolites produced in artificial environment are identical to those produced *in situ*, there are, however, several organisms, the metabolites of which are highly affected by the temporal and environmental changes. The transport and uptake of precursors are some other problems involved. Nutrient levels in the ocean are low. The concentrations of small organic molecules, such as amino acids and sugars, are generally from 0 to 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$. Uptake of precursor, therefore, occurs against a concentration gradient. Further, the biosynthesis of metabolites may occur at specialized sites or cells and the precursors must be transported to these sites intact. Marine organisms commonly live in symbiotic associations. For example, the association between sponges and microalgae or bacteria (or both) and that between coral and gorgonians is well-known. The pathway of transfer of nutrients between symbiotic partners is of great importance. The understanding of the metabolic process in the marine environment is still very limited. The nutrient levels in the ocean are normally of the micrograms per litre. The high concentrations of labelled precursors may overload the metabolic pathway. Further, the concentration of precursor may prove toxic to organisms. The use of cell-free extracts technique in marine biosynthetic studies is not very common, although it may resolve some of the problems, such as uptake and transport of precursors, effects of

symbiotic associations, etc. However, this technique is best suited where a reasonable rate of synthesis of metabolites is observed.

Several bioactive marine natural products are obtained in trace quantities. For example, to isolate 100 mg of bryostatin-2, an antileukaemic agent from the bryozoan *Bugularia* species, 1500 kg of the appropriate bryozoan is required. These compounds are probably produced by microorganisms growing on the surface of the organism.

In spite of several problems the biosynthetic studies had been conducted in carotenoids in halophilic bacteria, algal sterols, isocyanides and isothiocyanides in marine sponges, sponge sterols, cholesterol, sponge phospholipids, brominated fatty acids and arsenic containing compounds in macroalgae and biosynthetic pathways traced^{38,39}. Biosynthesis of bioactive marine natural products produced in minute quantities is a challenging problem. There is a lot of confusion regarding the origin of compounds of marine organisms living in symbiotic form or contaminated with bacteria. Feeding experiments are expected to resolve some of these problems. The biosynthesis of bioactive marine natural products is fascinating and challenging.

Marine organisms of the Andaman and Nicobar Islands

Sponges : About 70 species of marine sponges occur in the Andaman and Nicobar Islands. In recent past some very important compounds of biomedical interest had been isolated from marine sponges from different parts of the world. However, the marine sponges of the Andaman and Nicobar Island appear practically to have remained uninvestigated^{14,15}.

Anemones : Several species of sea anemones occur on the sea coast of the Andaman and Nicobar Islands. The toxins of sea anemones are generally polypeptides or proteins. Some of the toxins are inhibitors of proteinases. Some are found very useful tools for studying the voltage-dependent Na^+ channel in nerve, cardiac muscle cells. It has been suggested that coelenterate toxins would be suitable for studies of tumor cell cytotoxicity *in vitro* and *in vivo*. The toxins of coelenterates of the Islands need a thorough study.

Corals : The soft corals that occur in the Andaman and Nicobar Islands are horny gorgonians, sea fans, the red organ pipe coral, and the blue coral, *Helipora* etc. The common species that are found in the Islands are *Acropora* and *Porites*. The extracts of a number of corals from the Islands had been evaluated for broad biological activities and some of them had shown promising activities. *Zoanthus* species collected from the Visakhapatnam coast had yielded three new alkaloids zoanthamine, zoanthenamine and zoan-

thamide^{40,41}. Chemical investigation of corals from the Andaman and Nicobar Islands could furnish useful bioactive compounds.

Current status of bioactive metabolites

The marine sponges, jelly fishes, sea anemone, gorgonians, corals, bryozoans, molluscs, echinoderms, tunicate, and crustaceans during the last two decades had furnished a large variety of bioactive metabolites with unusual structures^{14,15}.

Investigation of sponges, jelly fish, sea anemones and corals had furnished bioactive sterols, steroidal alkaloids, terpenoids, isoprenylquinols, furanoids, sesquiterpenoids, triprenylphenols, compounds containing a guanino and a sulfone units. *Agelas* species had provided diterpenoids linked to a purine or a 9-methylpurine unit. These compounds displayed antimicrobial and Na, K, ATPase inhibitory activities. Avarol, a sesquiterpenoid from a Mediterranean sponge *Disidea avara*, was found active against AIDS virus.

A series of bioactive tricyclic diterpenes having isocyano, hydroxy, tetrahydropyranyl and chlorine functionalities and exhibiting antibiotic activity were isolated from *Acanthella* species. Many species of the genus *Spongia* contained biosynthetically intriguing C₂₁ difuranoterpenes probably derived from linear sesterpenoid antibiotics. Several norsesterpene peroxide antibiotics are obtained from the Red Sea sponges. Although sesqui-, di-, and sesterpenes are common in sponges, however, triterpenes are rare. Purealin, a novel enzyme activator from the Okinawan marine sponge, *Cliona celata* had yielded a series of linear peptide alkaloids. Marine sponges are also good source of bioactive nucleosides.

There has been much interest in the metabolites of jelly fishes. The nematocyst venom of the organisms had been studied in several cellular and subcellular tissue preparations. A lethal toxin from the *Chrysaora guinguecirraha* affected ion permeability in lipid membranes by producing monovalent cation channels. A cardiotoxin from the sea wasp had been purified by immunochromatography.

The sterol composition of several soft corals and gorgonians as well as the sterol composition of their associated symbiotic dinoflagellates had been studied. In general, highly oxygenated sterols often exhibit pharmacological activity. Pseudoterolide, a diterpenoid with 12-membered ring system, displayed unusual cytotoxicity.

Palythora spp. had furnished palytoxins, the most potent toxins known so far. *P. liseia* had yielded several metabolites exhibiting antineoplastic activity. The zoanthid *Gerardia savaglia* was found to be unexpected new rich

source of molting hormone ecdysterone. Several macrolides isolated from *Bugula neritina* had shown high order of antineoplastic activity.

Separation and isolation techniques

The extracts of marine organisms exhibiting biological activities could be a mixture of several class of compounds. Since the chemical nature of bioactive compounds of the complex mixture is not known it is not possible to follow any specific technique for the separation of the constituents of the complex mixture. However, a broad separation of the mixture can be achieved by fractionation with organic solvents. If the separation is good, the biological activity may concentrate in a particular fraction. Sometimes the biological activity may be in more than one fraction.

Generally lipophilic compounds extracted in hexane, benzene and chloroform, are esters, ethers, hydrocarbons of terpenoids, sterols, fatty acids etc. The mixtures of these compounds are resolved by standard chromatographic techniques over SiO₂, Al₂O₃, HPLC etc.

There are number of problems associated with the separation of water-soluble compounds. The abundance of salts carried over from seawater into the water extracts, makes the separation of water-soluble compounds more perplexing. In handling aqueous extracts of marine organisms, an inevitable problem is bacterial and fungal growth, which often degrades the active constituents or gives false results in bioassays due to endotoxins produced by microorganisms. It is particularly disturbing in antitumor activity screening because many endotoxins exhibit antitumor activities. Enzymes such as glycosidases, sulfatase, proteinase, and various oxidases are usually activated upon homogenization which can bring changes in some bioactive compounds and thus the activity may be lost. If heat does not destroy the activity, brief heating or autoclaving may alleviate the problem considerably.

While working with the aqueous extract of marine organisms, desalting is probably the most important and often the most difficult process. The presence of large amounts of inorganic salts gives rise to false results in bioassays. It also interferes in all chromatography systems including gel filtration.

The methods generally used in biochemistry for desalting are not applicable for the isolation of low molecular weight compounds from the aqueous extract of marine organisms. If the size of the inorganic ions and the low molecular weight compounds is not different, both the inorganic ions and desired compounds will appear almost at the same position on the desalting gels or membranes widely used in biochemical preparations.

The desalting of the freeze-dried residue of the aqueous extract of the marine organisms can be done conveniently and effectively by use of absolute methanol, followed by careful filtration through gels with small matrices such as Sephadex C₁-10 or Bio-Gel P-2. The small molecular weight compounds are thus desalted and separated. If the desired compound is reasonably hydrophobic, one may try other nonionic resins, such as XAD-2, XAD-7, polyethylene or polypropylene powder and porous polyether type resins. Filtration through small pore membranes usually gives imperfect separation of salt. Adsorption on active charcoal is also effective partially for desalting.

Generally, bioactive compounds of the total water-soluble organic portion and inorganic salt, is a very minor fraction. It is indeed a formidable task to isolate pure active compounds from the complex mixture. There is no established standard fractionation procedure for water-soluble compounds and one has to rely often on trial and error.

Ion exchange chromatography is the most effective method for separating water-soluble compounds, if the ionic character of the compounds and their stability on the resin and in buffer solutions are known. Choice of resins depends on the ionic character and stability of the target compounds on the resins. It should be noted that many compounds decompose on the H⁺ form of strong acidic resins or the OH⁻ form of strongly basic resins. Similarly, the strong pH of solutions used for elution often causes decomposition. The use of weakly acidic or basic resins or poorly buffered resins is preferred in such cases.

The compounds with wide range of polarity can be separated effectively on reverse-phase (RP) column with various hydrophobic stationary phase with the proper combination of organic solvents, such as MeOH and acetonitrile, and buffers. Successes are reported in biochemical analysis with almost all types of compounds. However, several problems are encountered when it is used for preparative purposes. First problem is that the sample size is very limited. The injection of large amounts of crude material results in the incapacitation of an expensive column. For this reason, the separation on reverse phase columns is usually done for the final purification or fine separation.

The second problem with reverse phase columns is the use of buffer solutions. For most polar or ionic compounds, to effect good separation and recoveries, the use of buffers with appropriate pH and ionic strengths is often unavoidable. In such cases, sometimes, the separation of minute compounds from the buffer may become a major problem. This can be overcome by the use of volatile buffers, which can be removed by vacuum evaporation or freeze-drying. It should be noted that the volatile buffers are also useful in

regular ion-exchange chromatography.

Combination of ion-exchange and size-exclusion chromatography is a very powerful separation technique. The separation is based on ion exchange, size exclusion, or hydrophobic/hydrophilic interactions. The selection of a proper matrix is the key for the successful separation.

Bioassay directed fractionation : The selection of an assay system to monitor fractionation is based on the original activity of the extract. *In vitro* tests are used in following the active compounds since they are rapid than *in vivo* tests and also the costs of bioassay are lower. For example, to follow anticancer activity, KB, L 1210 (LE) and P 388 (9 PS) cell lines are used to follow the progress of fractionation. The PS system *in vivo* is used only when the extract is not active in any of the *in vitro* systems.

Conclusions

The efforts of biologists and chemists over the last four decades have established the fields of marine peptides, nucleosides, alkaloids, prostanoids, terpenoids, polysaccharides, saponins etc. Most powerful toxins responsible for various types of poisoning have been isolated and characterized. Some of the most potent antineoplastic and antiviral compounds have been obtained from marine organisms. Didemnin-B, a cyclic depsipeptide from the tunicate *Trididemnum solidum*, is in Phase-II clinical trials. It is remarkably active as an immunosuppressant, some 1000 times as potent as cyclosporin-A in inhibiting T-cell mitogenesis. It has also shown *in vivo* activity in prolonging skin grafts. Spongoadenosine (Ara-A) from gorgonian *Eunicella cavolini*, is an effective drug in the therapy of herpes ketatitis, herpes encephalitis, and *Varicella zoster* infections in immunosuppressed patients. Ara-A is one of the best known antiviral drug in clinical use. It is interesting to note that Ara-A had been synthesized prior to its isolation from natural source.

India has a long coast line of 5800 miles rich in marine life. The marine life of the Andaman and Nicobar Islands is also very rich. There is hardly any work reported on the bioactive compounds of marine organisms of the Islands. There are ample opportunities for scientific exploration and discovery of new drugs.

Studies on marine natural products have enriched organic chemistry and widened the vision of biologists. Contributions to bioorganic chemistry, biosynthesis and discovery of new drugs are awaited.

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